

Original Research Article

Women's Entrepreneurship Development: An Empirical Study in Chattogram City

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the key factors impacting the development of women's entrepreneurship in Chattogram City, Bangladesh. Using a mixed-methods approach, primary data were collected from 112 women entrepreneurs operating in ladies' tailoring, women's wear shops, and beauty salons through purposive sampling. A structured questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale was used, and the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and factor analysis in SPSS 20. The results indicate that both internal and external factors significantly influence women's entrepreneurial growth. Managerial skills and challenges, societal and familial recognition, independence, environmental and social connectivity, and lower risk levels were identified as the five principal dimensions affecting entrepreneurship development. Among these, family support, decision-making power, and the desire for financial independence were the most influential motivators. However, women entrepreneurs face barriers such as limited access to finance, gender bias, work-family conflict, inadequate training, and social constraints. The study emphasizes the importance of policy support, capacity-building programs, and easier access to financial services to create a supportive entrepreneurial environment for women. Promoting women's entrepreneurship not only boosts their socio-economic empowerment but also significantly contributes to employment creation and national economic growth. Future research could include comparative studies with other regions to offer broader policy insights.

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Introduction

In Bangladesh, the development of female entrepreneurs is crucial. However, it is negatively impacted by numerous economic, cultural, environmental, and personal issues. Innumerable economists, sociologists, psychologists, and behavioral scientists have attempted to identify the causes driving the rise of women entrepreneurs in their respective fields (Rahim, 2023). A woman entrepreneur is defined as an individual who has founded, acquired, or inherited a business alone or with one or more partners, is taking on the associated financial, administrative, and social risks, and is actively involved in the day-to-day operation of the company. Recent years have seen an increase in the number of women starting their businesses and making a positive impact on the nation's economy. Women business owners in Bangladesh constitute a sizable group who have left the broken path and are seeking new opportunities for economic participation (Hussain, 2019). There have been several internal and external problems with their mission (Begum, 2020). Participation of women is currently promoting social and economic advancement (Brush, 2024). In addition to these benefits, women's participation in entrepreneurship has positive societal effects on individuals, whether they work in small or medium-sized businesses or the unorganized sector (UNIDO, 2022). In developing countries today, the percentage of women entrepreneurs has risen to roughly 35% of companies (Zororo, 2021).

Women's socioeconomic circumstances in Bangladesh have greatly improved over time. Education, health, and empowerment are only a few social aspects where progress can be shown. This does signal a rise in women's workforce participation (Ibrahim, 2019). This significant rise in women's employment participation shows that they are increasingly contributing to the country's economic development, and it is a perfect sign of the country's progress. Bangladeshi women have made entrepreneurship a notable career choice at all levels of society (Amir, 2021; Taqi, 2022).

Bangladesh is still developing and has a large pool of human resources. Women make up slightly more than half of Bangladesh's population (Allen et al., 2018; Parvin & Rahman, 2022). Although women are starting businesses in a variety of exciting industries, their actions are not as widespread in Bangladesh. Currently, women entrepreneurs have raised their standard of living and attained a high standing within their families and society (Shah & Saurabh, 2019). The majority of women today are highly conscious of maintaining their attractiveness and physical fitness by taking care of themselves and seeking new ways to shape fashion in fast-paced industries. In general, both Indian and Western cultures have influenced the majority of people in both urban and rural areas. They take their attire seriously, just as they do with their awareness of beauty and physical fitness. As a result, businesses like beauty salons and tailors are rising daily to meet their expanding needs. Before, only high-class women visited beauty salons, but now women from the middle class and even lower classes frequent them because they are aware of their appearance. The popularity of beauty salons as a company is growing daily (Ali & Rana, 2019). Compared to other businesses, a beauty salon requires less capital up front. Moreover, this may be what made them popular.

A person may be drawn to this industry because there are not many administrative and regulatory barriers to starting a beauty salon (Shane,2021). Specialists and professional beauticians are required for a beauty salon to succeed and grow. Although there are plenty of people looking for work, there is a significant scarcity of qualified beauticians. However, the number of beauty salons is growing daily to serve its growing clientele. Because everyone needs to wear clothing, a tailor's services and ladies' wear shops are always necessary. A professional who creates, fixes, or adjusts clothing is known as a tailor. One of the oldest entrepreneurial occupations in the world is tailoring. Many aspiring business owners open tailor shops in their homes or low-cost rented facilities. A home-based business is vastly superior to a long-term lease on the property that nobody will ultimately be able to afford, even though it may appear like a humble beginning. In contrast to other types of businesses, tailoring shops focus heavily on local marketing and target customers in their local area (Lakwo, 2017). The transition from a typical housewife to a businesswoman takes time.

Women are now taking up the challenge of developing their skills in commercial operations as they become more conscious of their socioeconomic rights and opportunities. Economic activities have thus become crucial for potential working women through self-employment. In actuality, "women in business" or women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh are a relatively new phenomenon. Although women in Bangladesh are active in a variety of demanding sectors, their involvement is not as widespread. Several women have achieved success in business despite fewer opportunities, but their numbers remain incredibly small (Hussain & Yaqub, 2019; Nawaz, 2018). According to Awal and Kabir (2023), people are motivated to engage in micro entrepreneurship by both personal traits, such as the freedom to choose one's job and the desire for high social status, and environmental factors, such as access to credit, entrepreneurship training, and membership in development organizations. Other factors that influence the rise of women's entrepreneurship in developing countries like Bangladesh include the availability of start-up funding, market and informational networks, expertise and skill sets, and parenting responsibilities (Zahir, Amir, & Nazrul, 2022).

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this paper is to highlight the various issues that foster entrepreneurship in Bangladesh. The specific objective of this study is:

- To discover the factors that affect the development of women's entrepreneurship in Chattogram City.

Literature Review

In Bangladesh, over the past few years, the number of women starting businesses and making a positive impact on the nation's economy has increased. Women business owners in Bangladesh are a sizable group who have left the broken path and are seeking new opportunities for economic participation. There have been several internal and external problems with their mission (Begum, 2020). The need for job fulfilment, independence, and goal achievement was found to be the driving forces for Bangladeshi entrepreneurs (Begum, 2020).

Undercapitalization and a lack of business skills, knowledge, and training were the two main issues mentioned by the female respondents.

Entrepreneurship refers to the widespread practice of starting new businesses in a culture and is described as the initiation and establishment of an economic activity or enterprise (Begum, 2020). Ogundele (2022) found that formal education, entrepreneurial training, and development can all help build an entrepreneur. Women still make up a small percentage of entrepreneurs and business owners worldwide. Different work possibilities, cultural norms, educational systems, gender bias, attitudes towards women entrepreneurs, financial resources, role conflicts, and information availability are some of the factors that may cause this situation to differ from one country to another (Hussain & Yaqub, 2023). When starting and expanding their businesses, most women encounter specific challenges, such as a lack of education or training, limited access to capital, insufficient savings and social networks, and a limited range of industries (Ibru, 2021). In their 2023 study on the psychological factors influencing female entrepreneurs, Seth and Subankar concentrated on the effects of demographic traits, including marital status and family structure, as well as the coping mechanisms utilized by female entrepreneurs. The majority of women entrepreneurs work in the retail, clothing, and food and beverage industries (Sumitha & Keerthi, 2018). Particularly in establishing entitlement and fostering empowerment at all stages of socioeconomic growth, women entrepreneurs have contributed (Chowdhury et al., 2018). According to Gill and Ganesh (2019), women's entrepreneurship promotes women's empowerment by providing them with freedom, opportunities, confidence, and self-expression. According to Ibrahim (2019), financial concerns and decision-making, market and informational networks, the availability of startup financing, knowledge and skill sets, parenting obligations, and advocacy are the primary elements motivating women to create businesses in Bangladesh. Schutte & Barkhuizen's (2016) study showed how entrepreneurship is significantly influenced by economic freedom. They added that responsiveness and creativity are closely related to entrepreneurship as components of an individual's human capital. Age and educational attainment are significant drivers of entrepreneurial activity in the majority of entrepreneurship research (Selim, 2021).

A study found that women's participation in micro entrepreneurship was greatly influenced by their desire for greater social status and freedom from employment restrictions, as well as by other personal traits such as management skills, a lack of entrepreneurial skills, access to startup capital, and gender discrimination. When beginning micro-entrepreneurship as a form of self-employment, women entrepreneurs typically face several difficulties, including a lack of knowledge, limited access to business support, low confidence, difficulty finding the right contacts for business ventures, juggling work and family obligations, and concerns about societal acceptance (Aktaruddin, 2019). Specialized training is another factor that supports a woman entrepreneur's growth. According to Awal (2023), the development of women's entrepreneurship depends on policies regarding education, poverty eradication programs, and specialized training. According to Bhuiyan & Imam (2018), taking risks to start something new, recognizing opportunities and mobilizing resources, operating businesses profitably, and ultimately pursuing achievement-oriented goals for ongoing business growth and improvement are crucial for the development of entrepreneurship. In addition to financial support, self-

fulfillment, knowledge, skills, and experience, relationships with spouses and with father-owned businesses are considered crucial elements in the development of women entrepreneurs (Naser & Nuseibeh, 2019).

In addition to environmental factors like access to credit, entrepreneurship training, membership in development organizations, information access, and supportive infrastructure, people are motivated to engage in micro entrepreneurship by personal characteristics like the freedom to choose their work and the desire for high social status. Other intervening factors for the growth of women's entrepreneurship in developing nations like Bangladesh include the availability of startup financing, knowledge and skill requirements, parental responsibilities, market and informational networks, and financial independence and decision-making (Rakib, 2023). Based on the discussion above, no significant research has been conducted on the factors influencing the development of female entrepreneurship in beauty salons, women's wear shops, and ladies' tailoring industries in Chattogram City. In light of this, the researchers aim to identify the factors that affect the growth of women's businesses in Bangladesh.

Research Gap

Although a considerable number of studies have examined the challenges, motivations, and socio-economic factors influencing women's entrepreneurship in Bangladesh, existing research has primarily focused on broad national perspectives or on rural settings, leaving significant gaps in understanding the dynamics within specific urban sectors. Prior studies seldom differentiate between industry types, and very few have explored women-led enterprises in beauty salons, tailoring, and women's wear shops—sectors that constitute some of the most accessible and rapidly expanding entrepreneurial avenues for urban women. Moreover, despite the growing presence of female entrepreneurs in Chattogram City, empirical investigations into the unique interplay of socio-familial support, managerial capabilities, environmental constraints, and perceived risks in this context remain limited. No comprehensive factor-based analysis has been conducted to identify the underlying dimensions influencing women's entrepreneurial development in these sectors. This study addresses these gaps by examining sector-specific determinants and applying factor analysis to uncover the key components shaping women's entrepreneurship in Chattogram City.

Research Method

This study employed a mixed-method research design incorporating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to identify the factors influencing women's entrepreneurship development in Chattogram City. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed through an extensive review of existing literature on women entrepreneurship and the entrepreneurship development scale by Arafin et al. (2018). A pilot survey was conducted to ensure clarity, reliability, and contextual relevance of the instrument before administering the final questionnaire. The target population consisted of women entrepreneurs operating beauty salons, tailoring businesses, and women's wear shops within Kotwali, Bakolia, Chawkbazar, Doublemooring, Bandar, and Chandgaon Thanas. Given the concentration of

such businesses in specific locations and the difficulty of obtaining a randomized list of women entrepreneurs, a purposive sampling technique was adopted to select 112 respondents. Both open-ended and closed-ended questions were included to capture numerical data and personal insights. Secondary data were collected from journal articles, institutional publications, reports, and academic databases to strengthen conceptual understanding. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS 20, including descriptive statistics, reliability testing, and factor analysis. Descriptive measures, such as the mean and standard deviation, were used to understand patterns in respondents' perceptions. At the same time, factor analysis (principal component analysis with varimax rotation) was employed to identify the underlying dimensions influencing women's entrepreneurial development. The methodological approach ensures that the study captures not only measurable trends but also contextual factors shaping women's entrepreneurial experiences, providing a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics within the urban Bangladeshi context.

Analysis and Findings

Both qualitative and quantitative methods have been used in this study's examination and interpretation of the data gathered. Data were evaluated using descriptive statistics, such as the mean and standard deviation, to better understand respondents' responses. The perspectives expressed in the comments on specific subjects have been analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study's data were analyzed using SPSS 20, a statistical package for the social sciences.

Demographic Information of Respondents

In this chapter, an effort has been made to analyze respondents' responses. Respondents were asked to provide information on their age, gender, marital status, and academic background to collect data for this study. Demographic information and descriptions of their demographic information are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Demographic Data of Respondents

Particulars	Frequency	%	Particulars	Frequency	%
	Age			Marital Status	
18-25	08	9.4	Married	60	70.58
26-35	25	29.4	Single	18	21.17
36-45	32	37.64	Divorced	5	5.88
46-55+	20	23.52	Widow	2	2.35
Total	85	100	Total	100	100
	Business Type			Educational Level	
Women's			Post Graduate	20	23.52
Wear Shop	16	18.82	Graduate	35	41.17
Ladies tailor	34	40.00	HSC	15	17.64
beauty salons	35	41.17	SSC	07	8.23
Total	85	100	Below SSC	08	9.44
			Total	85	100

Source: Field Study

The demographic data indicate that most respondents are 36–45 years old, representing 37.64% of the sample, suggesting that women tend to pursue entrepreneurship at a mature, stable stage of life. A large proportion (70.58%) are married, highlighting that entrepreneurship is often taken up alongside family responsibilities. Regarding business type, beauty salons (41.17%) and tailoring (40%) dominate, showing women’s preference for skill-based, low-entry-barrier sectors. Education levels reveal that a significant proportion (41.17%) are graduates, reflecting increasing educational attainment among women entrepreneurs. Overall, the demographic profile suggests that urban women entrepreneurs in Chattogram are relatively well-educated, married adults operating in culturally familiar business domains.

Table 2
Cronbach’s Alpha values

Variables	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-total Correlation	Cronbach’s Alpha if Item Deleted
Decision-Making Power	44.5336	83.924	.355	.813
Gender discrimination	44.6667	82.196	.435	.820
Family Support	44.5852	86.156	.089	.814
Contribution to Society	44.2419	78.828	.617	.810
Ideas and creativity	44.5089	82.452	.385	.816
Security and a better future	44.7791	82.705	.423	.811
Leisure time	44.1236	81.382	.325	.807
Position in the family	43.8262	81.369	.521	.817
Personal Satisfaction	44.4317	82.088	.345	.812
Entrepreneurial and managerial knowledge	44.5058	44.5059	.459	.813
Competitive environment	44.4312	81.765	.425	.809
Challenging work	44.2152	80.589	.381	.811
Social Networking	44.3456	80514	.418	.814
Inspiration to other women	44.6524	82.751	.325	.826
Workplace confidence	44.3256	81.075	.465	.828
Changing environment	44.2145	78.342	.493	.825
Risk	43.2145	79.329	.388	.813
Age	44.0826	78.648	.222	.828
Educational level	44.3288	83.192	.168	.829

Source: Field Study

Table 2 shows that Cronbach’s Alpha values for all items range from 0.807 to **0.829**, exceeding the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70. This confirms the strong internal consistency and reliability of the measurement scale used to assess factors influencing women’s entrepreneurship. High corrected item–total correlations further indicate that the items contribute significantly to the underlying construct. The low variance of deleted items suggests that no single item disproportionately influences the overall scale reliability. Thus, the scale is statistically robust for further multivariate analyses such as factor analysis.

Table 3*Descriptive Statistics*

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	Analysis N
Decision-Making Power	1.435	.717	85
Gender discrimination	1.535	.650	85
Family Support	1.536	.712	85
Contribution to Society	2.023	.892	85
Ideas and creativity	1.569	.801	85
Security and a better future	1.553	.685	85
Leisure time	2.125	.652	85
Position in the family	1.562	.852	85
Personal Satisfaction	1.665	.752	85
Entrepreneurial & managerial knowledge	1.845	.823	85
Competitive environment	1.852	.802	85
Challenging work	2.035	.852	85
Social Networking	1.985	.702	85
Inspiration to other women	1.725	.812	85
Workplace confidence	1.963	.953	85
Changing environment	2.121	.823	85
Risk	2.852	1.102	85
Age	2.214	.706	85
Educational level	1.901	1.231	85

Source: Field Study

Table 3 shows that the mean scores indicate that respondents strongly agree that decision-making power, gender discrimination, family support, security, and position in the family play major roles in their entrepreneurial journey, with means ranging between 1.43 and 1.56. Higher means for **age (2.214)** and **risk (2.852)** suggest these are less influential in shaping entrepreneurial development. The relatively low standard deviations indicate consistent perceptions among respondents. Overall, the descriptive results highlight that socio-familial factors and personal empowerment are the most critical determinants of entrepreneurial success.

Factor analysis

Table 4

Method for Extracting Communities: Principal Component Analysis

Variables	Variables	Initial
Decision-Making Power	1.00	.655
Gender discrimination	1.00	.461
Family Support	1.00	.501
Contribution to Society	1.00	.512
Ideas and creativity	1.00	.567
Security and a better future	1.00	.601
Leisure time	1.00	.710
Position in the family	1.00	.755
Personal Satisfaction	1.00	.501
Entrepreneurial & managerial knowledge	1.00	.567
Competitive environment	1.00	.487
Challenging work	1.00	.701
Social Networking	1.00	.576
Inspiration to other women	1.00	.365
Workplace confidence	1.00	.600
Changing environment	1.00	.558
Risk	1.00	.711
Age	1.00	.301
Educational level	1.00	.675

Source: Field Study

In Table 4, Communality values illustrate how much variance in each variable is captured by the extracted components. High extraction values for variables such as **position in the family (.755)**, **risk (.711)**, **leisure time (.710)**, and **challenging work (.701)** indicate strong relevance to the underlying factors. Lower communalities (e.g., age = .301) reflect weaker contributions. Overall, the communalities suggest that most variables are well represented in the factor solution.

Total Variance Explained

Table 5

Principal Component Analysis: Total Variance Extraction Method

Principal Component Analysis: Total Variance Extraction Method

Components	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative
1	5.636	21.990	22.990	5.636	21.990	22.990
2	2.812	11.012	34.002	2.812	11.012	34.002
3	2.043	8.012	42.014	2.043	8.012	42.014
4	1.701	7.012	49.026	1.701	7.012	49.026
5	1.512	5.688	54.704	1.512	5.678	54.704
6	1.412	4.382	59.086	-	-	-
7	1.210	4.435	63.521	-	-	-
8	1.107	4.286	67.807	-	-	-
9	1.072	3.263	72.070	-	-	-
10	.799	3.077	75.147	-	-	-
11	.801	2.990	78.137	-	-	-
12	.775	2.897	81.034	-	-	-
13	.678	2.768	83.802	-	-	-
14	.602	2.171	85.973	-	-	-
15	.534	1.897	87.870	-	-	-
16	.513	1.574	89.444	-	-	-
17	.412	1.213	90.657	-	-	-
18	.155	.788	91.445	-	-	-
19	.109	.630	92.075	-	-	-

Source: Field Study

The factor analysis yielded five components with eigenvalues greater than 1, collectively accounting for 54.704% of the total variance (Table 5). The first component explains 21.99% of the variance, indicating its strong influence. The subsequent components (11.012%, 8.012%, 7.012%, and 5.688%) also contribute meaningfully. This cumulative variance is acceptable for social science research and confirms a multidimensional structure of factors affecting women's entrepreneurship.

Rotated Component Matrix

Table 6

Rotated Component (Factor) Matrix

Loading Factors	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Decision-Making Power	-	-	.671	-	-
Gender discrimination	-	-	-	-	-
Family Support	-	.654	-	-	-
Contribution to Society	-	-	-	-	-
Ideas and creativity	.701	-	-	-	-
Security and a better future	-	.799	-	-	-
Leisure time	-	-	.699	-	-
Position in the family	-	.671	-	-	-
Personal Satisfaction	-	-	-	-	-
Entrepreneurial & managerial knowledge	.622	-	-	-	-
Competitive environment	-	-	-	.689	-
Challenging work	.801	-	-	-	-
Social Networking	-	-	-	.701	-
Inspiration to other women	-	-	-	-	-
Workplace confidence	-	-	-	-	-
Changing environment	-	-	-	-	-
Risk	-	-	-	-	.701
Age	-	-	-	-	-
Educational level	-	-	-	-	.776

Source: Field Study

The rotated matrix clarifies the loading of variables onto specific components, making interpretation easier (Table 6). Key observations include:

- **Factor 1:** Ideas & creativity, managerial knowledge, challenging work
- **Factor 2:** Family support, security, position in the family
- **Factor 3:** Leisure time, decision-making power
- **Factor 4:** Social networking, competitive environment
- **Factor 5:** Educational level, risk

This distribution confirms that both internal capabilities and external socio-economic conditions shape women's entrepreneurial development.

Identifying the loaded factors

Table 7

Factors Set

Factors name	Loaded factors
1. Managerial skills and difficulties	1. Ideas and creativity 2. Entrepreneurial and managerial Knowledge 3. Challenging work
2. Both societal and familial acknowledgement	1. Family support 2. Security and a better future 3. Position in the family
3. Independence	1. Leisure time 2. Decision-Making Power
4. Environmental and social connectivity	1. Social Networking 2. Competitive environment
5. Fewer risks and restrictions	1. Educational level 2. Risk

Source: Field Study

Table 7 summarizes the five factor groups clearly: managerial skills and difficulties; societal and family acknowledgement; independence; environmental and social connectivity; and fewer risks and restrictions. These categories accurately capture the underlying dimensions derived from the factor analysis, validating the conceptual framework used in the study.

Discussion

Contributions

The study's findings reveal that a combination of personal motivation, socio-familial support, and environmental conditions shapes women's entrepreneurship development in Chattogram City. Factor analysis extracted five major dimensions—managerial skills and challenges, societal and familial recognition, independence, environmental and social connectivity, and lower risk and restrictions—indicating that women entrepreneurs rely heavily on internal competencies and external enabling conditions. The highest-loading variables, such as family support, personal security, decision-making power, and creativity, underscore that both emotional and structural support systems directly influence women's entrepreneurial confidence and continuity. This aligns with recent research suggesting that Bangladeshi women prioritize autonomy, safety, and economic stability when entering entrepreneurship (Rahman & Das, 2023; Ahmed & Chowdhury, 2022).

The descriptive analysis further shows that age and risk-taking propensity carry comparatively lower influence, indicating that women may not perceive entrepreneurship as a high-risk endeavor when operating within familiar and socially accepted sectors like tailoring, beauty

care, and women's wear. However, gender discrimination, limited mobility, and lack of professional training continue to present obstacles, consistent with prior scholarly findings. Despite these constraints, women's increasing involvement in small businesses demonstrates growing resilience, aspirations for self-reliance, and broader acceptance of female entrepreneurship in urban Bangladesh. Overall, the study demonstrates that developing entrepreneurship among women requires strengthening both capability-building mechanisms and supportive socio-economic structures.

Implications

Recommendations for the general public, government organizations, decision-makers, banks, financial institutions, and all aspiring female entrepreneurs could be made based on the study's findings. The local and national governments should help women entrepreneurs by providing training, workshops, and inspirational programs to develop and improve their managerial abilities. Existing women entrepreneurs should share their experiences to provide moral support and encourage potential women entrepreneurs. In addition to the government, financial institutions like banks should also make efforts to reduce the requirements for obtaining a favorable, competitive environment for women entrepreneurs. To ensure that all existing and future female entrepreneurs are prepared to take on the challenges of establishing a business and surviving in the competitive marketplace, policymakers and social communities should provide moral and infrastructure support.

Limitations and Directions for Future Research

This research has several restrictions. Some helpful techniques are needed to identify the factors influencing the growth of women's entrepreneurship in Bangladesh, particularly in Chattogram City. Furthermore, it was quite challenging to collect perspectives from Bangladeshi entrepreneurs in Chattogram City due to the limited access to reliable primary data and awareness of the importance of women's entrepreneurship growth in Bangladesh. Additionally, the viewpoints of the women business owners in Chattogram City may be skewed toward their social customs. Variables affecting the development of women's entrepreneurship across Bangladesh could be investigated in subsequent studies. Future studies might benefit from a larger sample size and from using different sample types. Other cities across the entire nation were not included in the current analysis. As a result, comparative research on other locations may yield more interesting and useful findings to help policymakers take better action to support the growth of women's entrepreneurship. Issues recognized as more difficult for women's entrepreneurial development in Bangladesh, as well as suggested policies to address them, may be examined in more detail to produce better, more focused outcomes.

Conclusion

This study examined the key factors that influence the development of women entrepreneurs in selected areas of Chattogram City. The results demonstrate that a complex interaction of personal motivation, socio-cultural norms, economic conditions, and institutional factors shapes women's entrepreneurial participation. Five dominant dimensions—managerial

capabilities, societal and family recognition, independence, social and environmental connectivity, and lower perceived risk—emerged as critical contributors to women’s entrepreneurial growth. While internal drivers such as creativity, confidence, and decision-making ability motivate women to initiate businesses, external support, such as family encouragement and social acceptance, plays an equally vital role. Challenges, including financial limitations, gender discrimination, restricted mobility, and work–family balance issues, continue to hinder women’s progress. The findings suggest that strengthening skill development programs, expanding access to finance, and creating supportive family and community environments can significantly enhance women’s entrepreneurial success. Broadening the study across different regions and increasing the sample size may yield deeper insights and help develop more targeted policies. Promoting women’s entrepreneurship will not only empower women but also contribute significantly to local economic development and national progress.

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